

Challenges from selected sources used in the deductive phase of our data analysis

C. F. Barros *et al.*, "Large Language Model for Qualitative Research: A Systematic Mapping Study," *2025 IEEE/ACM International Workshop on Methodological Issues with Empirical Studies in Software Engineering (WSESE)*, Ottawa, ON, Canada, 2025

Challenges of Using LLMs in Qualitative Analysis (QA) Identified by Barros et al.

- Reliance on well-structured (or accurate) prompts for accurate results
- Tendency to generate "hallucinations" (responses without clear justification from the data)
- Inherent model biases, especially with sensitive information
- Difficulties in assigning topics to subjective expressions
- Lack of context sensitivity and emotional nuance
- Restrictions in interpreting complex meanings
- Excessive response over-segmentation and over-categorization
- Challenges in achieving coder consensus with ambiguous data, requiring human intervention
- Difficulties in broader and more detailed categorization, leading to loss of details valued by human researchers
- Inconsistencies in zero-shot classifications
- "Echo chamber" effect—reproducing pre-trained patterns
- Challenges in maintaining coder independence while fostering collaboration
- Risk of premature influence from LLM-generated coding suggestions, potentially biasing human coders

New **challenges in using LLMs for QA** drawn from recent papers on QA and LLMs (listed at the end).

- Problem with the token window length
- Need of a harmonization process to ensure consistency
- Restrictions in interpreting contextual nuances
- Subscription costs.
- Attempt to not analyze a large data set
- Miscategorization
- Lack of clarity in the decisions made by the LLM.

M. De Morais Leca, L. Valenca, R. Santos and R. De Souza Santos, "Applications and Implications of Large Language Models in Qualitative Analysis: A New Frontier for Empirical Software Engineering," in *2025 IEEE/ACM International Workshop on Methodological Issues with Empirical Studies in Software Engineering (WSESE)*, Ottawa, ON, Canada, 2025

Challenges of using LLMs in QA identified by Leca et al.

- Inconsistent results due to the stochastic nature of LLMs
- High sensitivity to prompt wording and input data
- Generation of hallucinations (incorrect or fabricated information)
- Lack of reliability for consistent analysis
- Difficulty capturing nuanced meanings and subtle contexts
- Limited ability to engage with complex theoretical frameworks
- Absence of reflexivity and interpretive depth
- Ethical concerns, including lack of consent and internal ethical framework

- Privacy risks when processing sensitive participant information
- Ethical challenges due to the black-box nature of model decision-making
- Lack of accountability for data processing of sensitive information
- Potential reinforcement of dominant perspectives and hegemonic knowledge
- Token size limitations restricting processing of large datasets or interviews
- High computational and resource demands, limiting accessibility
- Risk of technological and methodological dependency
- Inability to replicate human behaviors and interpretive nuances, risking loss of richness in qualitative analysis

K. R. Felizardo et al., "On the Difficulties of Conducting and Replicating Systematic Literature Reviews Studies Using LLMs in Software Engineering," 2025 IEEE/ACM International Workshop on Methodological Issues with Empirical Studies in Software Engineering (WSESE), Ottawa, ON, Canada, 2025

Selected **challenges in using LLMs for systematic reviews (SRs)**, as identified by Felizardo et al., relevant to QS:

- Prompt Sensitivity – small prompt changes affect results
- Randomness / Non-replicability – same prompt gives different answers
- Black-box / Transparency Issues – unknown training data & processes
- Model Drift / Version Changes – LLM config may change over time
- High Computational Cost – expensive to run & replicate

M. Binz, S. Alaniz, A. Roskies, B. Aczel, C.T. Bergstrom, C. Allen, D. Schad, D. Wulff, J.D. West, Q. Zhang, R.M. Shiffrin, S.J. Gershman, V. Popov, E.M. Bender, M. Marelli, M.M. Botvinick, Z. Akata, & E. Schulz, How should the advancement of large language models affect the practice of science?, Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A. 122 (5) e2401227121, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2401227121> (2025).

Challenges on using LLMs in Science identified in Binz et al.

- Hallucinations and fabricated information
- Risk of plagiarism and unclear attribution
- Accountability gap (cannot attribute responsibility to AI)
- Risk to reproducibility due to proprietary model updates
- Confidentiality risks when used for peer review
- LLMs can make mistakes and should not be blindly trusted
- Need for extensive verification of outputs
- Training data and model opacity make performance hard to evaluate
- Temptation to trade off quality for speed
- Bias amplification and fairness risks
- Risk of sidelining human understanding (epistemic concern)
- Risk of overuse simply because it is a universal tool
- Poor performance in logic and deductive reasoning
- Mistaking coherent LLM output for valid knowledge

References (new papers on QA and LLMs)

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- Sakaguchi, K., Sakama, R., & Watari, T. (2025). Evaluating ChatGPT in qualitative thematic analysis with human researchers in the Japanese clinical context and its cultural interpretation challenges: Comparative qualitative study. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 27, e71521.
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